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IMPACT OF MODERN INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES ON HUMAN HEALTH

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Annotation: In the course of the research, the concept of information security is considered. The influence of technologies on the general physiological state of a person is shown. As a result of the conducted research, it was found that despite the constant use of the Internet among respondents there is a relatively small risk of Internet addiction (about 15 %). Modern ICTs are still unsafe for the health of a large number of the population. At the heart of the disorders that develop with the constant use of computer technology are adverse changes in the functioning of the central nervous system. The analysis of publications shows that working with the use of modern computer technologies leads to the development of various functional disorders.

Keywords: information security, information and communication technologies, human health, functional disorders

Relevance. In the modern world, the role of the Internet as the main source of information, communication, and various entertainment resources is significantly increasing. The most effective means of ensuring personal information security is a high level of human information culture, that is, the ability to possess the following skills: the ability to clearly formulate their information needs, search and evaluation of information sources (identification of the most reliable, complete and operational) [1];

search, analysis, transformation, synthesis of information; evaluation of the effectiveness of the process of meeting information needs [2].

In addition to the psychological consequences of the impact of information and communication technologies (ICT) on people's lives, one should not forget about the indirect impact of ICT on human health [3].

The main factors of physiological effects ICT are electric and electrostatic fields, magnetic fields of low and ultra-low frequency, X-ray and ultraviolet radiation [4-8].

The purpose of the study. Consider the concept of information security and show the impact of technology on the general physiological state of a person.

Materials and methods of research. To identify the risk of Internet addiction among young people, the method of voluntary anonymous online testing was used, the respondents of which were students of higher educational institutions (a total of 40 people aged 18-20 who passed the survey). Search, comparative and evaluation methods were used, and an analysis of various scientific articles was also carried out, which examined the impact of modern computer technology on human health.

The results of the study and their discussion. According to the testing data, most of the respondents prefer to communicate in social networks in their free time (57.5 %) or visit Internet portals (62.5 %) for the purpose of: network games (15 %); watching videos, movies, YouTube channels, etc. (about 10 % in total). The vast majority (85 %) of people use the Internet (excluding study/work time) every day. Or at least 3-4 times a week (5 %). Less than half of the respondents (42.5 %) spend 3-4 hours on the Internet, slightly less – 35 % – 1-2 hours a day.

Only 12 % of respondents notice that they are often on the Internet longer than planned. Approximately 30 % are respondents who only occasionally notice such a trend. For the most part, while on the Internet, people experience relaxation (62.5 %). However, the majority of respondents (77.5 %) do not have negative emotions when they cannot access the Internet. For more than a third of respondents (37.5 %), Internet access is not a cause of problems with study or work, or it does not happen often (27.5 %).

According to studies of the physiological state, more than half (55 %) have no signs. The most common symptoms are:

- back pain – 22.5 %;
- restless sleep – 15 %;
- insomnia – 10 %.

The other signs: pain in the hands, numbness of the fingers, decreased visual acuity, pain in the eyes account for 2.5 %.

Conclusions. As a result of the conducted research, it was found that despite the constant use of the Internet among respondents there is a relatively small risk of Internet addiction (about 15 %).

Over the past decade, computer technologies have undergone significant changes in their structure (in particular, the electromagnetic radiation of video monitors has been reduced, a significant part of video terminals has been replaced with monitors with liquid crystal screens). Nevertheless, modern ICTs (as well as other technologies too) are still unsafe for the health of a large number of the population [4-8]. In this study, it was found that adverse changes in the functioning of the central nervous system are the basis of disorders that develop with the constant use of computer technologies.

The analysis of modern publications shows that prolonged hard work with the use of modern computer technologies leads to the development of various functional disorders of the musculoskeletal and visual systems, a decrease in the effectiveness of the activity performed.

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